

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

School heads' managerial skills for effective administration: Relationship to teachers' job performance in public elementary schools

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International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 15(01), 565-583

Publication history: Received on 25 February 2025; revised on 07 April 2025; accepted on 09 April 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.15.1.0991>

Abstract

The study centered on determining the relationship between the school heads' managerial skills for effective administration and the teachers' job performance of 17 school heads and 209 teachers in public elementary school of Quezon District. This study made use of the descriptive-correlation research method. Descriptively, found out that school heads' showcase managerial skills for effective administration in terms of communication skills, human relations, and technical skills. Findings also revealed that the public elementary school teachers usually perform their job effectively and behaviorally. Relatively, the teachers' job performance was influenced by the communication skill of school heads for effective administration.

Keywords: School Heads; Managerial Skills; Job Performance; Teacher Performance; Communication Skills; Descriptive-Correlation Research

1. Introduction

Leading the schools depends much on the heads of the institutions. They require them to exhibit managerial skills to be an agent of change to for a school as a culture of excellence. According to Aquino et al., (2021) as an are agents of change through their abilities in management they can contribute a major impression on the educational milieu through their information-sharing methods, creating supportive social connections, participating in mentoring programs, and fostering progress. Successful schools are the results of competent governance demonstrated by the school heads in collaborative partnerships with relevant stakeholders (Leithwood et al., 2020; Teddy, 2016). This is comparable to the argument of Pont et al., (2008) that the primary role of school leadership is to encourage, gauge, and enrich the efficiency of teachers. Further, school officials are those who have the power to produce and disseminate new information quickly and to maximize their access to educational opportunities and networks (Hannah & Lester, 2009; Fields et al., 2019). As such, productive schools have school administrators who dedicate a significant amount of time to planning and overseeing instruction; are extremely visible in the school and remain loyal to the learning environment (Simmons & Taylor, 2019). The school head is the central figure around which other aspects of the institution revolve. He is accountable for all aspects of the system's operation, whether academic or administrative. The school head must be inclined to make almost all the school's decisions (Gumus, 2019). A trustworthy school head would use collaboration as a working technique by establishing teams and smaller units of team members to examine proposals or tactics (Chen et al., 2007). Therefore, it is up to the school head to be a strong team player to impact on the quality of instruction (Brenninkmeyer & Spillane, 2008; Hacker & Roberts, 2003).

Best quality instruction and teacher competence can be directly or indirectly influenced by the managerial skills of their school leaders (Brenninkmeyer & Spillane, 2008; Hallinger & Ko, 2016). Managerial skills are the mode of conduct that the leader embraces in affecting the performance of the teacher because educational success could only be accomplished by fulfilled and inspired teachers (Sebastian et al., 2017). Authentic leadership abilities are a pattern of actions that

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school leaders display in influencing teachers' conduct towards achieving organizational and personal expectations (Malik et al., 2010). A successful form of management is thus essential to inspire teachers and enhance their productivity in schools (Teddy, 2016; Elangovan et al., 2010).

Research has shown that the standard of leadership creates a peculiarity between the gains and losses of a school (Mangundjaya, 2015; Matte et al., 2015). In high-efficiency educational institutions that have overcome the pattern of lower productivity and decreasing performance, school officials set the benchmark by directing and encouraging teachers and employees to reach their highest potentials (Gandolfi & Stone, 2016). Schools, as such, make a significant difference to educational outcomes; the motivational strategies of school heads are among the reasons that contributed to student success (Hallinger & Heck, 2010). Other school-related considerations that should be addressed by the school heads due to their impact on students' learning and educational aspirations include the teacher's extent of coaching and supervised learning, the standards of teachers, the method of leadership and teaching practices, and the trends and practice and attributes of the school setting (Yariv & Kass, 2019). Mustafa and Othman (2010) have found that there can be a clear connection between efficiency and teachers' work performance. They noted that teachers showed better performance if the intensity of commitment is better. Thus, when teachers are incredibly motivated, the success of their work becomes significant (Aziz et al., 2018).

1.1. Theoretical Framework

This study will be anchored on Katz's Managerial Skills Theory. Katz, in his 3 Skills Taxonomy, categorized skills as follows (Gordon, 2024): Conceptual - Conceptual skill involves the formulation of ideas. School Heads should create ideas, grasp abstract relationships, and creatively solve issues. Human talent has the capacity for good interaction with people. School leaders should engage in interactions and teamwork with the staff. Technical skill is knowledge of methods, or technique and competency. Heads of schools should apply the tools, methods, and procedures of a certain field. One of the factors behind recurrent organizational achievements is managerial competence. Efficiency and effectiveness in management call for managerial competencies. Triplet managerial skills clarify to reconsider educational programs and selection of management in future (Afshari et al., 2012)

1.2. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Paradigm Showing the Relationship between the Independent and Dependent Variables

The preceding theory affirms that the school heads managerial skills which have a favorable impact on teacher performance; thus, if principals have stronger managerial skills, teachers' performance will increase (Patarusi, 2017). The level of education is affected by how well school staff, like teachers and principals, do their jobs. By keeping an eye on teachers all the time, leaders should create an environment that helps teachers get better at what they do. It would also encourage the system's members to develop good interpersonal ties, work together, and be motivated to achieve school objectives (Giami & Obiechina, 2019).

Conceptually, Figure 1 illustrates the procedural flow of the research addressing relationship of IV and DV. The model of the study applied both dependent and independent variables. The idea focused on the interaction of IV, which

embodies the administrative abilities of school leaders, and the DV, which reflects teachers' job performance, how does it affect each other for successful teaching and learning?

1.3. Statement of the Problem

The study aims to investigate the relationship of school heads' managerial skills to teachers' job performance in public elementary schools.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

- How may the school heads' managerial skills be described in terms of:
 - Communication skills
 - Human relation skills; and
 - Technical skills?
- How may the teachers' job performance in public elementary school be described?
- 3. Is there a significant relationship between school heads' managerial skill to teachers' job performance in public elementary schools?

1.4. Hypothesis

The null hypothesis will be tested at 0.05 level of significance:

There is no significant relationship between school heads' managerial skill to teachers' job performance in public elementary schools.

1.5. Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study will focus on assessing the correlation between the managerial abilities of school heads and the job performance of teachers in public elementary schools. The survey would involve 209 public elementary school teachers and 17 heads of schools from Quezon District as respondents.

1.6. Significance of Study

The performance of elementary school instructors could be much influenced by the evaluation of managerial abilities of school heads. Effective administration depends on the ability of the school to identify the factors influencing the leadership and management enemy. Through better teaching and learning for holistic development of students, it can result in improved and raised school performance. By means of managerial abilities, school heads can improve their adaptation to their surroundings and to the personnel under their direction. One of the most important abilities that aspirant leaders should acquire in their growth is the flexibility of their management approach. The institution can set guidelines and expectations for first-rate education as well as the growing learning environment for teachers and students. Knowing the managerial skills and the work performance of elementary school teachers would help schools to profit from their ability to lead and steer the institution in every event that is happening to change the teaching and learning environment for the learners to increase performance. This study will thus enable the institution to empower managerial abilities and enhance performance leading quality instruction of teachers to benefit students.

1.7. Operational Definition of Terms

The following definitions have been established since they will be applied in the research:

- **Managerial Skills.** It's about how school leaders should be able to set goals and get things done, necessitating a distinctive array of abilities and characteristics including confidence, making choices and fixing problems, which culminate in positive performance, emphasizing communication skills, interpersonal skills, and technical expertise.
- **Teachers' Job Performance.** Pertains to the specific role of educator in handling classroom management to achieve good performance obtaining results in quantity, quality, efficiency and effectiveness in school.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research Design

Since the purpose of the research is to assess the relationship between school heads managerial skills and teachers' job performance of public elementary schools, this study used descriptive correlational design. Descriptive correlational

research is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect (Bhat, 2023). It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them. According to Stangor & Walinga (2019) it is a research design using specific methods such as to collect, analyze, and interpret data. According to Mc Combes (2020), a correlational research design measures a relationship between two variables without the researcher controlling either of them or allows researchers to observe natural behaviors without affecting them in any way. May and Wood (2017), refer correlation to a statistical relationship between two or more variables, where a change in one variable is associated with a change in another variable. Hence, surveys are an efficient method for gathering large amounts of information about such things as individuals' experiences, beliefs, and attitudes (Miksza et al., 2023).

2.2. Locale of the Study

This study will be conducted through 209 public elementary school teachers and 17 school heads of Quezon District, Quezon, Nueva Ecija.

The Municipality of Quezon is a 4th class municipality in the province of Nueva Ecija, Philippines that was named from the 2nd president of the Philippines, Manuel L. Quezon. According to the 2020 census, it has a population of 41,845 people (Census of Population, 2020).

Figure 2 Map of Quezon Nueva Ecija where the schools are located

2.3. Respondents of the Study

The study will focus on 209 public elementary school teachers and 17 school heads of Quezon District. The researcher will use the total enumeration as shown in Table 1 distribution of respondents and subjects per school:

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents and subjects per School

Name of Schools	Subjects	(School Heads)	No. of	Respondents	%
Bertese Elementary School	1		14		6.7
Casanova Elementary School	1		10		4.78
Dona Lucia Elementary School	1		9		4.31
Labong Elementary School	1		8		3.83
Osmena Elementary School	1		8		3.83
Pulong Bahay Elementary School	1		9		4.31
Quezon Integrated School	1		31		14.83
Ricardo L. Joson Elementary School	1		8		3.83
San Alejandro Integrated School	1		16		7.66
San Andres, I Integrated School	1		14		6.7

San Andres II Elementary School	1	8	3.83
San Manuel Elementary School	1	9	4.31
San Miguel Elementary School	1	10	4.78
Sta Rita Elementary School	1	12	5.74
Sto Cristo Elementary School	1	8	3.83
Sto. Tomas Feria Elementary School	1	11	5.26
Tomas Joson Elementary School	1	24	11.48
Total	17	209	100

2.4. The Instrument

The survey questionnaire checklist will be the main tool to be used in this study. According to Amedahe & Asamoah (2008), the questionnaire is a very concise, replanted set of questions designed to yield specific information to meet a particular need for research information about a pertinent topic, and it has the response options for the respondents (Sincer, 2012). The instrument consisted of two parts:

Part I. A validated questionnaire on Managerial Skills Possessed by School Head for Effective Administration (Asiyai & Akporehe, 2023) was adapted. The purpose of the questionnaire is to examine the managerial skills of school heads in three different dimensions: communication skills, human relation skills, and technical skills. The instrument was patterned to response scale of 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 4 (Strongly Agree).

Part II. The validated questionnaire on Teachers' Job Performance Scale (Asiyai & Akporehe, 2023) measures how teachers perform on the specific tasks for teaching and learning. The instrument was patterned to response scale of 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Rarely) to 4 (Usually).

2.5. Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was adapted and permitted by the researcher/ developer to be used for research purposes in education. Hence, it does not require to test the validity and reliability.

2.5.1. Administration of the Instrument

Before the administration of the questionnaire, written permissions were signed by the Dean of Graduate School to conduct the study. The researcher will also secure permission to the Schools Division Superintendent, Public Schools District Supervisor, and from the school heads of different schools. The instrument will be converted into google docs and shared to respondents for safe and fastest administration of instrument to solicit relevant data and information needed in the study.

2.6. Statistical Treatment of Data

After collecting the data needed, all responses regarding the study will be tabulated, tallied, ranked, and interpreted verbally with the help of statistical tools and treatment. The researcher will use descriptive-correlational to describe and determine if there is a correlation between the independent and dependent variables.

The researcher will use the following statistical treatment:

- To describe the teachers' digital competence and teaching performance of teachers: frequency count, mean, and percentage will be used.
- Spearman Rho will also use it to determine the association between ordinal and interval or ratio variables.

3. Results and discussion

This section presents the results and discussions of the study based on the generated data following the research paradigm and the problem statement of the study.

3.1. School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration

3.1.1. Communication Skills

Table 2 exhibits the mean responses of teachers on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of communication skills.

Table 2 Mean Responses of Teachers on School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration in Terms of Communication Skills

Indicators	Mean	VD
Listens to learners' complaints	3.10	<i>Agree</i>
Communicates school goals, mission and vision	3.83	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Communicates school policies clearly	3.89	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Shows ability to modify school practice for quality delivery	3.54	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Ensures proper coordination of works by communicating effectively	3.74	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Makes clear school procedures to teaching and non-teaching staff	3.40	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Clarifies information through verbal communication	3.30	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Keeps every stake holder informed about the challenges of the school	3.35	<i>Agree</i>
Cooperates with staff and learners	3.20	<i>Agree</i>
Listens to teachers' ideas	3.27	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>3.46</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
<i>1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 = Disagree, 2.51 -3.25 = Agree, 3.26-4.00 = Strongly Agree</i>		

The data reveals that teachers strongly agree on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of communication skills (WM = 3.46). Teachers highly believe that their school head communicates school policies clearly (mean = 3.89); communicates school goals, mission and vision (mean = 3.83); ensures proper coordination of works by communicating effectively (mean = 3.74); shows ability to modify school practice for quality delivery (mean = 3.54); makes clear school procedures to teaching and non-teaching staff (mean = 3.40); keeps every stakeholder informed about the challenges of the school (mean = 3.35); clarifies information through verbal communication (mean = 3.30); listens to teachers' ideas (mean = 3.27); cooperates with staff and learners (mean = 3.20); and listens to learners' complaints (mean = 3.10)

For effective administration, school heads as justified by their teachers used to communicate school policies based on goals, mission and vision and through proper coordination of works, intends to modify school practice for quality delivery of the teaching and non-teaching staff by collaborating with stakeholders about challenges and clarifying information through verbal communication, listen to ideas to cooperate and solve complaints. Communication is essential in school environments. However, it's critical for school heads to be able to communicate effectively with their teaching staff where they can ensure that people feel valued and motivated in the work they're doing. Indeed Editorial Team (2024) pointed out that school heads s can accomplish systematic communication through written communication like notes or emails as well as one-on-one conversations; by conveying messages to others and listening with the intention of understanding; School heads can nurture feelings of trust, additionally, teaching staff are more likely to feel close to their school heads if they are willing to share their own personal perspectives and feelings and encourage others to do the same.

Communicatively, school heads might be able to communicate based on vision and mission in various ways. Managing communications effectively is a key dimension of leadership. According to Educational Leaders (2024) communication underpins the knowledge, skills and dispositions school heads require to have a direct and indirect influence on teachers and student outcomes. Public school heads today manage people, data, and processes and they are tasked with setting goals and motivating constituents to meet these goals. Hence, the quality of personnel, teachers, and school heads communication has a significant impact on student test scores (Cullen et al., 2013). Coursera Staff (2024) stated that conveying and receiving information through a range of verbal and non-verbal or other means is important in a team,

it is important to deliver a presentation at work, brainstorm with coworkers, address a problem, or confirm details about the project where they are an essential part of communication developing positive professional relationships. Indeed, school heads nowadays apply a range of formal and informal communication skills every day. Communications may be deliberately planned or ad hoc; face to face or virtual; written, video or verbal; digital or non-digital (Educational Leaders, 2024). School heads set the tone and standards for interactions with staff, faculty, students and the community; they're an important link between the education system, learners, teachers and parents. EdwardsVille (2022) pointed out that school heads play a significant role in defining the school's atmosphere and culture while influencing the faculty's attitude towards their students by means of communication skills. A school can be a welcoming place where learners not only learn but are also challenged, encouraged and supported. Hence, school heads must have strong communication skills to lead effectively.

Skillful communication has been broadly accepted as an important leadership attribute across disciplines. Scholars have focused much attention on the study and practice of communication skills in the fields of education (Goby & Lewis, 2000; Makoul, 2001). McEwan's (2003) research identified the role of communicators as the number one most important element of highly effective school heads. Tyler (2016) examined self-reported principal communication strategies and explored the nature of school leadership and the importance of communication for building a vision and encouraging stakeholders to work toward such a vision. The communication strategies practiced by most or all of the school heads further uncovered themes of communication in leadership which include a student-centered approach to decision-making, transparency of decision-making, shared decision-making with school head and teachers, the role of faculty trust, and principal preparation. Specific principal communication behaviors with teachers were implemented in motivating teachers toward earning high-performing status. Oguejiofor (2023) in his study found that school heads' communication skills are necessary and indispensable in the achievement of effective leadership. Specifically, verbal communication skills can predict effective leadership to a high extent, written communication skills can predict to a very high extent while listening communication skills can predict effective leadership to a low extent.

3.2. Human Relations

Table 3 exhibits the mean responses of teachers on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of human relations.

As seen in the table, teachers strongly agree on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of human relations (WM = 3.43). They certainly believed that their school heads have the ability to work as a team (mean = 3.71); ability to include staff in decision making (mean = 3.60); ability for being approachable (mean = 3.57); having a caring attitude (mean = 3.43); ability to understand others (mean = 3.33); ability for being friendly with staff (mean = 3.25); and ability to call staff by their names (mean = 3.15).

Based on the above findings, teachers highly believe that their school heads have the skills to work as a team in decision making, approachable with a caring attitude to understanding others who's friendly knowing how to call staff by their names. A school head is the leader of the school and must showcase these skills in all aspects. According to Vasquez (2022) the school head needs to be able to manage a large teaching staff and still stand as a human relation officer to staff and all learners. Human relations skills are essential and help school heads expertly guide both staff and learners effectively (Vasquez, 2022).

Human relations skills are critical for developing and maintaining a positive work environment, retaining employees and encouraging productivity. By making human relations the focus of management approach, school heads can effectively create a workplace culture in which the teaching staff can thrive through management style which is human relations centric (Indeed Editorial Team, 2024). Human relations are inseparable from communication, and good communication happens when there is good feedback, instruction and transparency (Manullang, 2017). Mutual respect in school will grow a good relationship among human beings (Onong Uchjana Effendy, 2007). Human Relation is a harmonious relationship, created because of awareness and willingness to incorporate individual's desire to address common interests (Manullang, 2017). Therefore, Human Relation among all stakeholders in a company will get the work that fall under the individual or mutual responsibility done effectively, which eventually leads to increased job satisfaction felt by individuals who work in that organization (Hasibuan, 2012). According to Onong Uchjana Effendy (2007), Human Relation is defined as human relations instead of human relations. According to Yuningsih (2011), human relation serves as preventing misunderstanding between leaders and subordinates, developing cooperation between leaders and their subordinates, establishing teamwork effectively, mobilizing individuals in a group towards achieving a goal.

Table 3 Mean Responses of Teachers on School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration in Terms of Human Relations

Indicators	Mean	VD
Ability to call staff by their names	3.15	<i>Agree</i>
Having a caring attitude	3.43	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Ability for being approachable	3.57	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Ability to include staff in decision making	3.60	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Ability to work as a team	3.71	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Ability for being friendly with staff	3.25	<i>Agree</i>
Ability to understand others	3.33	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
<i>Weighted Mean</i>	3.43	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
<i>1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 = Disagree, 2.51 -3.25 = Agree, 3.26-4.00 = Strongly Agree</i>		

In a facilitating school, the school principal is the person who tries to help teachers achieve, rather than to monitor and control their behaviors (Armağan, Öz & sever, 2020). This situation, which can be evaluated as strategies of school principals to exceed the bureaucratic form, was interpreted as maintaining dialogue with teachers through a professional approach rather than a bureaucratic approach in Tschannen-Moran (2009). According to Armağan, Öz & Sever (2020) the school gains a facilitating organizational character as professional orientation increases; it gains prohibitory organization character as bureaucratic orientation and authoritarianism increase. In facilitating school structure, problems are seen as opportunities to learn, teachers are trusted, cooperation is supported, ways of helping to succeed are sought, and making decisions together is considered important (Armağan, Öz & sever, 2020). In short, by giving teachers sufficient autonomy to carry out their work, the conflict between the authority based on bureaucracy and the authority based on professional norms in educational organizations is prevented (Abbott & Caracheo, 2000; Lunenburg & Ornstein, 2013). Northouse's (2013) finds that the school head initiates human relations, establishes ties and has the burden of maintaining the relationship in the relationship between leader and follower reminds the conditions in which dialogues of facilitating school principal with the environment are positive.

3.2.1. Technical Skills

Table 4 exhibits the mean responses of teachers on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of technical skills.

Table 4 Mean Responses of Teachers on School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration in Terms of Technical Skills

Indicators	Mean	VD
Able to apply modern methods in solving problems	3.55	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Encourages teachers use of modern tools	3.30	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Employs innovation in school administration	3.67	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Able to conduct structured interview	2.85	<i>Agree</i>
Able to make strategic plan for solving school problems	3.42	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
Able to set rules and regulations for school operation	3.25	<i>Agree</i>
Analyze school issues critically	3.20	<i>Agree</i>
<i>Weighted Mean</i>	3.32	<i>Strongly Agree</i>
<i>1.00-1.75 = Strongly Disagree, 1.76-2.50 = Disagree, 2.51 -3.25 = Agree, 3.26-4.00 = Strongly Agree</i>		

Descriptively, data reveals that teachers strongly agree on school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of technical skills (WM = 3.32). Technically, they usually observe their school head who is able to apply modern methods in solving problems (mean = 3.55); encourages teachers use of modern tools (mean = 3.30); employs innovation in school administration (mean = 3.67); able to conduct structured interview (mean = 2.85); able to make strategic plan for solving school problems (mean = 3.42); able to set rules and regulations for school operation (mean = 3.25); and analyze school issues critically (mean = 3.20)

Data deduced that school heads use their technical skills to manage their school for effective administration. Their teachers perceived that they focus on modern methods in solving problems and encourage teachers to use it by employing innovation and conduct structured interviews to make strategic plan setting rules and regulations to analyze school issues critically. Indeed, school heads technically manage their school with their people. Technical skill is the ability to perform tasks satisfactorily in a specialized area or discipline. Katz (2002) defined technical skills as the capability and competency to carry out work or job in a particular specialty. Technical skills are the ability of a school head to know and undertake duties effectively using the acquired specific techniques, activities, and processes needed for certain operations in schools (Phiri, 2019). Technical skills consist of proficiency, knowledge, techniques or processes in a certain specialized profession like in school administration (Kermally, 2013). The skills are significant at the lower levels of administrative because the school heads are dealing with members of staff performing their duties. Technical skills comprise school heads' knowledge of the kind of work that under her must undertake. It is also concerned about personal proficiency and knowledge in any form of technique or process (Cheluch et al., 2024). These forms of competencies and skills appear to be significant at lower levels of administration, their comparative as part of administrative role decreases as school heads move to higher echelons of leadership (Namgyal, 2022).

Technical skill is crucial for productivity of the school heads to the extent to which a school head knows and applies technical skill in solving managerial problems goes a long way in determining the success of the school (Nwogu & Ebonu, 2019). Ghalandari et al., (2012) opined that technical skills enable the school heads to supervise and effectively coordinate instructional aspects of school administration. Technical skill include the ability to conduct structured interview during recruitment, ability to engage in short and long term strategic planning, ability to work on curriculum and extract the required scheme for the terms and sessions, ability to analyze and set-out rules and regulations, procedures and protocols governing the school's operations, ability to forecast and project the income and expenditures of the school in the light of economic and political realities, budgeting and costing and controlling capabilities as well as the ability to resolve conflict in the school among others (Nwogu & Ebonu, 2019). These abilities aid the school heads in handling administrative matters smoothly (Robinson et al., 2009).

The importance of technical skills calls for professionalization of school heads to equip them properly for discharging their responsibilities effectively and this has become apparently imperative given the perceived poor or lack of technical ability demonstrated by some school heads (Nwogu & Ebonu, 2019). This has evidently resulted in ineffective administration of such schools. Ndu (2004) observed with dismay the poor administration of some schools and blamed it on poor technical skill among school heads. Oluremi (2013) asserted that school heads should not only be trained in the art of administration alone but also should be trained on principles of administrative control. Katz (2000) recognized that school heads need to have a thorough understanding and attitude for a specialized activity, especially one that involves techniques, procedures, processes, and methods. This is because technical skills involve processes and working with physical objects (Werang et al., 2023). Technical skills assist school heads to utilize different tools and machines effectively (Akporehe & Asiyai, 2023). In schools, heads who have technical skills offer professional guidance to teachers to advance to a higher-level self-confidence, enthusiasm, and effectiveness (Olorisade et al., 2023). The outcome of school head's application of technical skills is that there is favorable environment which is key to attainment of better classroom learning (Awtseana, 2019).

3.3. Teachers' Job Performance in Public Elementary Schools

Table 5 exhibits the mean responses on teachers' job performance in public elementary schools.

Table 5 Mean Responses on Teachers' Job Performance in Public Elementary Schools

Indicators	Mean	VD
Able to contextualize and localize the curriculum	3.65	<i>Usually</i>
Able to us and adapt various teaching learning strategies	3.60	<i>Usually</i>
Able to use relevant instructional material for academic activities	3.55	<i>Usually</i>

Able to use and interpret data driven result	3.45	<i>Usually</i>
Able to conduct teaching and learning remediation	3.40	<i>Usually</i>
Able to conceptualize research and learning intervention	3.35	<i>Usually</i>
Able and committed to school vision and mission	3.85	<i>Usually</i>
Able to create school climate for quality students learning	3.80	<i>Usually</i>
Able to use innovative instructional strategies	3.75	<i>Usually</i>
Able to ensure student active engagement during teaching and learning	3.70	<i>Usually</i>
Able to control and manage students' undesirable behavior	3.15	<i>Often</i>
Able and value punctuality to class to teach students	3.10	<i>Often</i>
Able to use and enhance the HOTS of students	3.25	<i>Often</i>
Able to use the different questioning styles	3.20	<i>Often</i>
Able to display good knowledge of subject matter	3.30	<i>Usually</i>
Able to conduct proper classroom assessment	3.51	<i>Usually</i>
<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>3.48</i>	<i>Usually</i>
<i>1.00-1.75 = Rarely, 1.76-2.50 = Sometimes, 2.51 -3.25 = Often, 3.26-4.00 = Usually</i>		

Empirically, data reveals that teachers usually perform their job in public elementary schools (WM = 3.44). Public elementary school teachers believe with high extent that they are able and committed to school vision and mission (mean = 3.85); able to create school climate for quality students learning (mean = 3.80); able to use innovative instructional strategies (mean = 3.75); able to ensure student active engagement during teaching and learning (mean = 3.70); able to contextualize and localize the curriculum (mean = 3.65); able to use and adapt various teaching learning strategies (mean = 3.60); able to use relevant instructional material for academic activities (mean = 3.55); able to conduct proper classroom assessment (mean = 3.51); able to use and interpret data driven result (mean = 3.45); able to conduct teaching and learning remediation (mean = 3.40); able to conceptualize research and learning intervention (mean = 3.35); able to display good knowledge of subject matter (mean = 3.30); able to use and enhance the HOTS of learners (mean = 3.25); able to use the different questioning styles (mean = 3.20); able to control and manage students' undesirable behavior (mean = 3.15); able and value punctuality to class to teach students (mean = 3.10).

Based on the findings, pertaining to job performance, public elementary school teachers are committed to school vision and mission in creating school learning environment using innovative instructional strategies that ensure student active engagement through contextualization and localization of curriculum adapting various teaching learning strategies and relevant instructional material for academic activities. Hence, teachers conduct proper classroom assessment with interpreted data driven results as basis in conducting teaching and learning remediation that requires research conceptualization and learning intervention. Teachers are indeed exhibiting good knowledge of subject matter and enhance the HOTS of learners using the art of questioning where they can control and manage undesirable behavior and valuing punctuality to class to teach learners.

Public elementary school teachers in Quezon District perform their tasks accordingly. Hence, the ability of school through the school head to continue their operations and achieve their goals depends largely on teachers' job performance. Job performance is a behavior in which teachers engage and performing their work (Jex & Britt, 2008) or as measurable actions, behaviors and outputs directly engaged in or indirectly caused by teachers to serve school organizational objectives (Viswesvaran & Ones, 2000). Motowidlo (2003) states that job performance is the expected total value of behavioral episodes displayed by the teachers at a given period. According to Jamal (2007) job performance is the extent to which teachers can carry out their teaching-learning tasks successfully using the organizational resources under regular conditions. Whereas public elementary school teachers' job performance conceptually performed in terms of their behavior and outcomes produced by them for their learners.

Indeed, in teachers' job performance should be based on vision and mission, and core values of the school. As stated, teachers facilitate learning and constantly nurture every learner (DepEd, 2024). Teachers in doing their tasks are guided

by the vision, mission and core values of the DepEd. They used to involve all stakeholders where it leads to creating a school climate for quality learning. School climate is based on patterns of learners', parents' and school personnel's experience of school life and reflects norms, goals, values, interpersonal relationships, teaching and learning practices, and organizational structures (NSCC, 2024). Teachers use innovative instructional strategies as their instructional approaches that involve the use of technology, hands-on activities, and other materials to help learners learn in a meaningful way. By providing a variety of different instructional strategies and materials, teachers can boost student engagement and achievement in the classroom and these strategies focus on engaging students and encouraging them to take an active role in their learning (Strobel Education, 2024).

Through the contextualized and localized curriculum, teachers deliver the curriculum through localization and contextualization. The principle of localization and contextualization is not new to teachers for it is already embedded in mission which states to protect and promote the right of every Filipino to quality, equitable, culture-based, and complete basic education (Liquigan, 2014). That is being performed through the knowledge and initiative of teachers to choose the right strategies, materials for learning and engaging learners in improving the HOTS. One of the main 21st century components that teachers want their learners to use is higher-order thinking and this is when learners use complex ways to think about what they are learning (Cox, 2019) with proper classroom assessment of teachers as basis to conduct learning enrichment and remediation. Teachers take the initiative in organizing remedial classes to achieve expected competencies in core academic skills such as literacy and numeracy. Remedial instructions can help struggling learners shore up their basic skills and reduce the gap between what a student knows and what he's expected to know. Similarly, the Enrichment classes are held for scholar learners in the main subjects and help these self-motivated students to reach the pinnacle of new heights in their academics.

3.3.1. Relationship Between School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Elementary School

Table 6 exhibits the relationship between school heads' managerial skills for effective administration and teachers' job performance in public elementary school

Teachers' job performance of public elementary school teachers established significant relationship with school heads' managerial skills for effective administration in terms of communication ($r = .754^*$, p -value = 0.000) at .05 probability level, 2 tailed test.

Table 6 Relationship Between School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration and Teachers' Job Performance in Public Elementary School

School Heads' Managerial Skills for Effective Administration	Teachers' Job Performance	
Communication Skills	r	.754*
	p-value	0.031
Human Relations	r	-0.344
	p-value	0.405
Technical Skills	r	-0.131
	p-value	0.756
* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).		

Inferentially, the statistical result justified that teachers' job performance could be influenced by the communication skills of school heads for effective administration. Teachers in accomplishing their tasks should be guided by the effective communication skills of school heads. One important factor in the success of an educational institution is the school head ability as an effective communicator (Asriadi, 2020; Mashabi, 2020; Mulyadi, 2015). Effective communication in schools is necessary considering that everything that is done must be through agreement in deliberation (Lubis et al., 2023; Mesiono et al., 2023; Rolan, 2020). Effective communication between school heads and teachers is an important factor in building trust and mutual support. School heads are expected to be able to communicate well, listen empathetically, and provide constructive feedback to teachers who tend to have higher levels of trust and participation (Saniyah et al., 2023). Apart from that, school heads also need to be able to communicate clearly the school's vision, mission and goals to teachers, thereby providing clear direction in efforts to improve the

quality of education. Therefore, school heads need open and transparent communication so that it has a broad impact on teacher quality. When leaders encourage effective communication, teachers feel more comfortable sharing experiences, challenges, and innovative ideas (Maolana, Darmiyanti, & Abidin, 2023).

School head is a leader who plays an important role in introducing effective and innovative practices which ultimately guarantee the quality of learning in schools (Bafadal & Arifin, 2020; Dinham, 2005; Guvhu, Jita, & Akintunde, 2021; Urick, 2016). To make this happen, school heads need to build effective communication with class teachers and other levels. Because the school head's effective communication can increase and grow motivation, as well as the performance of teachers and all stakeholders in general (Mashabi, 2020). The teacher's performance in question is not only focused on achieving the results of teaching tasks such as school administration which includes creating syllabi, learning plans and assessments, but also regarding the behavior of an educator that is seen and exemplified by learners at school. Teacher performance in learning is the most important part in supporting the creation of an effective educational process, especially in building discipline and the quality of learning outcomes. Good teacher performance can create effectiveness and efficiency in learning and can shape the discipline of learners at school and the teachers themselves (Bergold & Steinmayr, 2023; Redding, 2019).

Several studies have shown a significant relationship between school heads' communication and teachers' job performance (Yodiq, 2016). Such research was conducted by Kartini, Ahmad, and Eddy (2020) which examined the influence of school heads interpersonal communication on teachers' job performance. Resulted that the school heads' interpersonal communication had a significant effect on teachers' job performance. Furthermore, research conducted by Harsono and Prasetyo (2021) conducted research on school heads and teachers through structured interviews resulted in the school heads' communication with teachers being in accordance with the school heads' communication dimensions in improving teacher performance by providing personal and group attention, maintaining good communication and relationships with teachers to create relationships. harmonious, safe and enjoyable work. Likewise, Pramahsari & Triatna (2020) conducted a study finding showed that the school heads communication had a significant impact on teacher performance. In contrast to previous research, research conducted by Nisa et al., (2023) shows that school heads still experience problems in communication management.

School heads communication skills in improving the responsibility of teachers is inter-personal communication and communication in solving problems that may arise in learning in order to improve teaching-learning performance. Forms of teacher responsibility in learning, include as a teacher, mentor, classroom administrator, curriculum development, professional development and fostering public relations. The teacher is also responsible for all attitudes, behaviors, practices of the protégé, responsibility towards him, his colleagues, school heads, parents of learners and others (Ärlestig, 2008). Hence, teacher performance can be improved through communication conducted by the school heads. School heads can apply various approaches in communicating vision, mission, and work programs to teachers to participate and carry out according to the instructions given and the communication approach can be supportive, emotive, reflective, and directive according to the condition and characteristics of the teacher (Pramahsari & Triatna, 2020).

4. Conclusion

The study demonstrated that principals in public primary schools had managerial competencies—specifically in communication, interpersonal connections, and technical skills—which substantially affect teachers' work performance, especially via communication. Educators typically indicated a high degree of job performance, suggesting that good leadership is favorably associated with productive teaching practices. These findings underscore the essential importance of school leaders' managerial competencies in cultivating a supportive and effective educational atmosphere. This study enhances the comprehension of school leadership's influence on teacher efficacy and can inform training programs designed to improve managerial competencies among school administrators. This study ultimately enhances societal welfare by advancing excellent education through improved leadership and facilitates additional investigation into school administration techniques and teacher development.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Pursuing a master's degree is a challenging yet rewarding endeavor, akin to scaling the summit of a towering mountain. Along the way, one encounters numerous obstacles that test one's resilience and determination.

I am deeply grateful to the many individuals whose support and guidance were instrumental in making this thesis a reality.

First and foremost, I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my mentor and advisor, Professor Ramil P. Polintan, PhD., for his unwavering support, patience, and invaluable expertise. His guidance throughout the entire research process, from the initial stages to the final defense, was invaluable.

I am also indebted to San Jose Christian College, Inc., particularly Ms. Annabelle A. Tarroza, President, and Dr. Felina L. Cariaga, Dean of Graduate Studies, for their support and encouragement.

I would like to extend my heartfelt thanks to the esteemed members of my thesis committee, Professor Tristan Ray L. Manzano, EdD., Professor Emmanuel L. Cariaga, PhD., Professor Perfecto V. Dizon Jr., PhD., and Professor Ligaya R. Bernardo, PhD. Their insightful feedback and expert guidance were invaluable in shaping this research.

I am grateful to my colleagues at San Miguel Elementary School for their encouragement and support, which motivated me to persevere.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The author declares that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this manuscript.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was acquired from all individual subjects involved in the study. Before participation, the research's goal, the techniques involved, and the voluntary nature of involvement were explicitly communicated to all participants. Participants were guaranteed the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses, as well as the freedom to withdraw from the study at any moment without repercussions. Consent was recorded through the completion of survey forms disseminated using Google Forms, which had a consent section affirming their acceptance to partake in the research

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